

Improving School Nurse Confidence with CGM Technology

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Background

- Continuous Glucose Monitoring (CGM) improves glycemic values in children
- CGMs = new pediatric standard of care
- Type 1 Diabetes (T1D) = 3rd most common school health condition
- School nurses lack familiarity with CGM devices & technology

Problem

- No standardized policy & procedure for CGM assessment exists
- School nurses receive no standardized training in CGM use
- Nurses' variable CGM interpretations jeopardize T1D care at school

Purpose

- Increase school nurse confidence in providing care for students with T1D by developing a standardized CGM protocol

Frameworks

- Overarching guide: Framework for 21st Century School Nursing Practice
- Multi-step approach to change: Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice

References

Methods

Participants: School nurses enrolled in the School Nurse Services Credential Program at CSUF

Design:

- Mixed-methods
- Descriptive, cross-sectional surveys
- Open-ended questionnaire regarding facilitators & barriers to CGM protocol implementation

Setting: Virtual via Qualtrics

Measurement tools:

Adapted Diabetes Device Confidence Scale (DDCS)

Results

Demographics

- n = 33 survey participants
- School nursing experience:

Qualitative

- Administrative support is a facilitator to implementation
 - Time constraints are barrier to implementation
- "new hires and nurses have very little training"*

Quantitative

- Difference between pre-DDCS & post-DDCS
- Paired t-test (p -value < 0.001)

Discussion

- CGM protocol statistically improved school nurse confidence in diabetes device usage
- Educational module was successful in improving school nurse confidence in CGM use for T1D students
- Emerging qualitative themes determined that administrative staff in collaboration with school nurses within the K-12 educational environment have the authority, resources, and time to update and enforce adherence to a standardized CGM protocol

Recommendations

- Simplify CGM protocol to address time constraints caused by school nurses' heavy caseloads
- Tailor to administrative staff who have the opportunity to enforce adherence to CGM protocol

Limitations

- Small sample size
- Questionnaire nonresponse bias
- Self-reported assessment of skills & knowledge

Future Implications

- Address gaps in glycemic sensor knowledge with standardized training for school nurses

Sustainability

- CGM educational module is available online for free:

Conclusion

- Providing a standardized approach to CGM assessment among school nurses improves the safety of students with diabetes at school